

THE ROW COURT REFURBISHMENT PROJECT

Project background:

The Row Court was a medium-sized domestic project, specifically a row housing scheme at the rear of an expensive Manhattan Victorian Development. The property was sold to an owner who wanted to convert it to a residence for himself and his children. It was a long linear external service quarters type, garage fair that has been sold off for a residential use. The original property was a narrow two-story building with a limited room space. The Client requested for an increased room space which resulted in a basement excavation as well as a conversion of the existing mono-pitch roof to a mansard roof type to increase the room space at the first floor of the building.

Exhibit 1: Front elevation of existing Row Court building

The cost of the project was £1.5 million. The Client first approached Predios, an Architectural firm about his intention for a refurbishment. The Client was not aware of Construction Design and Management (CDM) (i.e. health and safety [H&S]) issues. Support regarding CDM duties was mainly provided by Predios, the Lead Designer (i.e. an Architectural firm). The Client was mindful of his financial constraints and wanted to proceed, regarding the procurement, in such a way that he would have the opportunity early enough, particularly at the pre-construction stage of the procurement, to discontinue the project if the cost was found to be far above what he had planned for. This view led to the choice of the traditional procurement strategy where Designers were first engaged to handle the design component and Contractors invited to tender for the project.

There was no formal briefing document from the Client to the Lead Designer. The Client initially informed the Lead Designer about his intention to have the property refurbished for a residence and as well indicated the allowable budget. As an inexperienced Client, he was assisted by the Lead Designer to develop a brief collaboratively, having regard to the allowable budget. A project management firm, Emerald Ltd, was engaged by the Client to support him in engaging the Lead Designer to develop the brief as well as the entire project.

Following the project brief development, a Designer CDM Options Matrix – indicating right from the outset how H&S would be managed on the project – was developed. See Exhibits 5a – 5i for excerpts of the Designer CDM Options Matrix.

Client's General H&S Arrangements

The Project Manager assisted the Client to appoint the Lead Designer (i.e Project Architect). They went through RIBA membership list to find out chartered Architects with reasonable experience. The Lead Designer at the beginning of the procurement process indicated to the Client the peculiar H&S risks associated with the property refurbishment and the need for a Principal Designer (PD) to coordinate and manage H&S risks, particularly at the pre-construction stage. The Client subsequently appointed the Lead Designer, on a separate contract, to the PD role by using the Association for Project Safety (APS) contract for PDs. The level or scope of the PD's service on the project was largely informed by what specifically the CDM Regulations required of entities appointed to such a role. The PD was engaged on the project from the design stage through to construction and handover. The Lead Designer recommended for appointments, other Designers such as Structural Engineer and Services Engineer for structural and building services works, respectively. These were Designers who had worked with the Lead Designer on similar projects in the past. The need for the basement, which required the existing building to be underpinned, as well the mansard roof type necessitated the advice or involvement of a Structural Engineer right from the outset of the project design. Further, the Lead Designer assisted the Client to competency-assess the Designers appointed to the project. They had a standard questionnaire in place to carry out this function. The questionnaire was sent out to the prospective Designers to complete and return. See Exhibit 2 for a copy of the standard questionnaire. Face-to-face interviews sessions were organised with the prospective Designers by the PD, with the Client and the Project Manager in attendance, to defend their responses to the standard questionnaire. Emphasis, regarding the competence assessment, was specifically placed on similar experiences and projects in respect of the prospective dutyholders' portfolio.

The Principal Contractor (PC) was appointed by the Client through the assistance of the Project Manager and the PD. This happened through a competitive tender review process. The PC was the main Contractor on the project. Similar to the Designers, the PC was also assessed by completing a standard questionnaire. Exhibit 3 indicates the questionnaire used for accessing the PC. The involvement of the PD in the selection of the PC highlights a practice in the industry where PDs carry out 'competency checking' function under the PD role. Though the CDM 2015 does not require this of the PD, they often do it as Client expectation. Further, one of the key elements of the CDM Regulations 2015 is the appointment of the right people at the right time on the project to secure H&S. This phenomenon also accentuates a common approach (i.e. bespoke use of repeat appointment of dutyholders already assessed for skills,

knowledge, experience (SKE) and organisational capability (OC)) in the industry regarding assembling the project supply chain with focus on H&S.

The PD services fee was a percentage of the contract sum and was relatively higher than a new build due to the volume of H&S work associated with refurbishment projects. The percentage value was informed by the PD's time at meetings, time involved in producing H&S-related information, analysis of project site, and efforts required to research into survey information. Further, the Designers also made allowance for extra duties under the CDM but normally absorbed them under the general design duty fees.

The PD, subsequent to site visit and analysis, recommended asbestos and refurbishment surveys to be done by the Client on the project. Again, some of the timber members were lead painted. The PD thus recommended for a lead paint survey. Prior to the lead paint survey, the PD received an express instruction from the Client to authorise the removal of all lead-painted timber members from the building.

The PD in a design team meeting raised issues about the construction site set up plan, having regard to the site and access restrictions at the Row Court. The specific issues included vehicular access, car parking, welfare facilities, site storage, mobile crane location, waste skip location, and building services reuse during construction. Pointers to these issues and related information were provided by the PD to support the preparation of an effective Construction Phase Plan (CPP) by the PC. Further, at the design team meeting, attention was drawn to the need for an appropriate scaffolding with arrest net during the roof construction. How high-level windows on walls and mansard roofs ought to be cleaned by the maintenance team during building usage was indicated and discussed by the PD at the design team meeting. Holes in floors, service risers and ducts and how they ought to be protected were discussed as well. Again, big and heavy blocks were envisaged to be used on the project and a discussion on how they needed to be handled to avoid workers health being adversely affected were discussed. Additionally, how dust generally from demolition and cutting were to be managed were raised by the PD and discussed. The PD advised and recommended that large, long and heavy steel members for the mansard roof be spliced into reasonable lengths for smaller-sized cranes to lift into positions and thereafter bolted or joined together.

The active role played by the PD at the pre-construction stage of the project development process, as expected by the CDM Regulations 2015, in support of the Client to secure H&S on the project underlines one of the approaches employed by Clients when confronted with the regulatory requirement of having to make suitable arrangements to secure H&S on the project – use of third party H&S professional service providers such as PD, CDM Advisors, and H&S consultants.

Organisation:

There was no specific organogram for the management of H&S on the project. Instead, a simple responsibility matrix indicating the major professional services and the responsible entities was used. This matrix was also indicated on the Designer CDM Options Matrix. The entities indicated in the simple responsibility matrix contributed to the development of the Designer CDM Options Matrix through the offering of H&S suggestions at design team meetings. A sample of the simple responsibility matrix is indicated in Exhibit 4.

Principal CDM Documents Preparation:

Essentially, there was no separate effort regarding the preparation of the Pre-construction Information (PCI) pack. Arrangement regarding this regulatory requirement was subsumed by the preparation of the Designer CDM Options Matrix, which started at the outset of the design when the PD was appointed. It identified all hazards and significant risks on the project and proposed measures to manage them. This tool (i.e. Designer CDM Options Matrix) employed a blend of images and text narrations in communicating hazards, identified significant H&S risks as well as their proposed management measures. Specifically, the tool indicated the following hazards and significant H&S risks on the project:

- A highlighted site boundaries within the Row Court development enclave in relation to other existing features.
- Indication of a subterranean river tunnel underneath the access road adjoining the property.
- Access and exit restrictions to the site due to the presence of some narrow arch ways which had implications for certain construction equipment and vehicles accessing the site.
- Drawings of the existing property showing the state of the ground floor plan, first floor plan, and the roof plan
- Planning conditions and construction times
- Scheme drawings indicating the proposed or future state of the building with attendant H&S implications.
- Structural drawings or details.
- Minor building strip out details that exposed the state of building members or elements during surveys and prior to complete strip out by Contractor

Excerpts of the CDM Options Matrix, indicating some of the PCI, are shown in Exhibits 5a – 5i.

The Designer CDM Options Matrix was supplied to all tenderers. The idea was to have them prepare the CPP in response to the PCI indicated in the Designer CDM Options Matrix and submit together with the tender. The appropriateness or quality of response to the project H&S risks via the CPP was considered in the overall decision in selecting the suitable main contractor/PC for the project. Exhibit 6 indicates a checklist used for the review of the CPP.

The preparation of the Health and Safety File (HSF) started at the outset with the development of the Designer CDM Options Matrix where, relevant project H&S information were captured. The contents of the HSF file for the project included:

- Contract drawings
- As-built drawings
- Structural design information and details
- Residual H&S risks
- Information on windows and gutters cleaning (i.e. complex maintenance issues)
- Operation & maintenance (O&M) manuals
- Specification details or information on materials built into the structure. For example the type of fire doors, the type of plasterboard, etc.

Essentially, all the information in the Designer CDM Options Matrix, except the minor H&S safety practices required to be employed by the contractor during the construction stage, were included in the HSF. Examples of the minor H&S practices included usage and positioning of ladders, handling of heavy blocks by workers, among others. There was a seamless flow of information from the Designer CDM options matrix into the HSF. The challenge of obtaining as-built drawings from relevant project parties for the HSF, as often the case in the industry, did not arise as the PD kept a close and good working relationship with all the project parties and succeeded in ensuring an effective contribution to H&S by all project parties via the CDM Options Matrix tool.

Coordination:

The coordination of the inputs from all other dutyholders were handled through design team meetings where other project issues including H&S were discussed. The mansard roof profile and the basement development presented structural, services and architectural challenges with implications for H&S. Significant design team meeting times were devoted to discussing how to achieve an optimal solution while securing H&S of construction workers as well as the maintenance team during the life span of the building. For instance, considering the restricted location of a roof gutter abutting an existing high wall, it was agreed among the design team to have a construction process where the construction workers could first work on the gutter from the inside of the second floor before the roof covering is constructed. Again, for maintenance of the restricted roof gutter, an openable roof was provided in the mansard roof. The restricted roof gutter and the openable roof light in the mansard roof are indicated in Exhibit 7. Further, the PD ensured a coordination among the design team members, particularly the structural engineer and the services engineer, regarding the basement construction and an existing sewer.

The main challenges with coordination stemmed from planning issues where planning authorities did not permit an increment of the height of an upstand to a roof gutter due to its blockage of sunlight into an adjoining private property. See Exhibit 9b for the specific location of the potential sunlight blockage. Another related to access to an existing sewer. Negotiations on these challenges with the authorities concerned prolonged the project duration by three months which increased the time spent and the associated cost on the project in respect of the PD services, given the fixed price nature of the project.

Design team meetings on the project, particularly at the pre-construction stage, were planned on two weekly basis – initially – to address very complex design issues with implications for H&S. Specific examples of such complexities were the mansard roof and basement designs. Subsequently, when complex design issues were resolved, design team meetings were held monthly at the pre-construction stage. The Project Manager called for design team meetings but the Lead Designer coordinated and chaired the meetings.

The Project Manager, Designers (i.e. Project Architect, Structural Engineer, Services Engineer, and Quantity Surveyor) were often in attendance at design team meetings. The Client did not often attend meetings as he delegated his interest to the Project Manager. The agenda for design team meetings included: architectural, structural and building services drawings developed till date, the issues with them and implications for H&S; sustainability issues; building control issues and their implications for H&S. Generally, a standard architectural agenda, which

included CDM issues, was adopted for design team meetings. Exhibit 8 indicates the standard architectural agenda.

The main tool that was used for managing design H&S risk was the Designer CDM Options Matrix. This document highlighted hazards and significant risks with the design and the project generally. Further, it indicated the proposed risk control or management approach; project team member required to provide information for the management of risk; and the project team member with responsibility for the risk management. This document was often populated and updated after design team meetings and shared with all design team members subsequently.

There were no significant challenges with the design coordination as the Designer CDM Options Matrix tool resolved most of the design coordination challenges. The only challenge was the extended negotiations with the planning authorities and local residence regarding the construction of the roof and the attendant gutter abutting the party wall. See Exhibit 9a for an indication of the proposed original roof design – which was easy to construct – and the compromised design due to planning regulation requirement that was more challenging to build and maintain afterwards.

Conclusions and Lessons:

The H&S risks associated with refurbishment projects are relatively high. This requires conscientiousness, on the part of project participants including the Client, to secure H&S of all persons affected by the project. Though the CDM Regulations 2015 is relatively ‘gentle’ regarding Clients’ duties towards H&S, the project Client took steps to expressly appoint a PD to plan, manage and monitor H&S-related matters, particularly at the pre-construction stage of the project development process. The PD’s efforts were largely underpinned by the deployment of the Designer CDM Options Matrix. Several lessons precipitate from this case as follows:

- The project brief as an input to the Designer CDM Options Matrix ensured a seamless interaction between the Client’s initial requirements and tools used for effective H&S management. In that sense, a symbiotic relationship is established between the Client brief and H&S arrangements on the project. This offers an opportunity for the two (i.e. Client brief and H&S arrangements) to evolve together throughout the project development process to secure H&S.
- The use of a Designer CDM Options Matrix, which is a blend of pictures and narrations, instead of a normal spreadsheet was an effective approach to communicating, highlighting and managing H&S risks on the project.
- Having tenderers to submit CPP as part of tenders in response to the information indicated in the Designer CDM Options Matrix document avoided a generic CPP and ensured an effective CPP for the project. It also ensured certainty in the project cost – at least from the perspective of the Main Contractor who doubled as the PC – as the CPP was weighed into the decision making regarding the agreed upon price at tender.
- Aligning the Lead Designer role with the PD role, specifically integrating the Lead Designer decision making process with the CDM requirements, was a useful one in managing H&S on the project.
- Uncertainties such as planning restrictions and other matters can potentially extend project durations beyond initially agreed ones. It will thus be prudent for PDs to adopt

PD services' pricing approaches that will lend themselves to project shocks in order not to undermine effective PD efforts on projects.

EXHIBITS

Exhibit 2: A sample of standard questionnaire for Designers' organisational capability assessment

1 Company Details	Response/Comment
1.1 Company Name:	
1.2 Head Office (Registered Office):	
1.3 Correspondence address (if different to above):	
1.4 Date trading commenced:	
1.5 Type of Company (Limited, partnership sole trader, etc.):	
1.6 Contact Details:	
2 Types of Service(s) Provided	
2.1 Services Provided:	
2.2 Please provide details of similar projects undertaken by yourselves:	
3 Health & Safety (H&S) Policy	
3.1 Please provide a copy of your current general H&S policy statement:	
3.2 Please provide a copy of your management organisation chart highlighting those with H&S responsibilities:	
3.3 Please provide details of your company management system, in particular your H&S management system and other arrangements for putting the H&S policy into effect:	
4 Insurance	
4.1 Please provide a copy of your insurance certificate that applies to the work you perform or intend to perform for..... (e.g. Employers Liability, Public Liability, Contractors All Risks, Construction Plant and Professional Indemnity):	
4.2 Has your Insurer made any conditions on your policy within the last 3 years? (If so, please provide details):	
Construction (Design and Management) Regulations 2015 (CDM 2015)	
5.1 Please confirm you understand the requirements of Regulation 8 of the CDM 2015 and explain how your organisation meets them.	

5.2 Please confirm you understand the requirements of Regulations 9 and 10 of the CDM 2015 and explain how your organisation meets them.	
5.3 Please confirm you understand the general principles of prevention. Please give examples of how you achieve these during your works.	
5.4 Please provide details on how your organisation deals with foreseeable risks to the health or safety of any persons – (a) Carrying out or liable to be affected by construction work (b) Maintaining or cleaning a structure (c) Using a structure as a workplace	
5.5 Please provide details on how you communicate to other parties such as the Client, Principal Designer, Principal Contractor and other Designers to provide them with information about the design, construction or maintenance of structures.	
6 Health and Safety Resources	
6.1 Please provide relevant H&S certification for the members of staff involved in these types of project:	
6.2 Please provide the names and qualifications of internal H&S advisors and/external H&S consultants used by your organisation:	
6.3 Please outline any specialist resources which are utilised by your organisation in an advisory capacity in H&S:	
6.4 Please describe how each member of the team is communicated with, so that they are aware of his/her responsibilities under the CDM 2015.	
7 Training and Information	
7.1 Please provide details of Designers H&S training, in particular training focusing on health and safety in design.	
7.2 Please provide details of your CPD programme.	
7.3 Please provide details of key project personnel [Names, CV's, qualifications, memberships etc]	
7.4 Please provide evidence of the Designers experience with similar projects.	
7.5 Provide brief details of similar design projects undertaken [locations, description, dates, size and cost]	

7.6 Provide references from those who have engaged the Designers on similar projects	
8 Resources and Workforce Involvement	
8.1 Please outline how you allocate sufficient time and resources when planning and delivering projects you are engaged in	
8.2 Please provide details of the number of competent personnel available to work on the projects	
8.3 Please provide details of design and technical support facilities [e.g. computing, health and safety guidance, specialist technical links with external experts etc]	
8.4 Please provide evidence of health and safety consultation with the workforce [names of safety representatives, records of health and safety meetings/committees etc]	
9 Monitoring, Audit and Review	
9.1 Please provide details of the monitoring, audit and review procedures for your H&S systems. Including evidence of any audits that the management responses.	
10 Hazard Elimination and Risk Control	
10.1 Please Provide details on how you ensure co-operation with the design team, other designers, contractors and the Principal Designer.	
10.2 Please provide details on how hazards are eliminated and any remaining risks are controlled including examples of your design risk assessment system.	
10.3 Please provide examples of how risks have been reduced by your designs.	
10.4 Please provide confirmation that any structure used as a workplace will meet the requirements of the Workplace [Health Safety and Welfare] Regulations 1992. Please provide examples on how this has been achieved on projects you have carried out.	
10.5 Please provide details on how you will provide adequate information with your designs and information needed for the health and safety file.	

11 Sub-Contracting/Consulting Procedures	
11.1 Please provide evidence showing how you ensure sub-contractors/consultants have sufficient skills, knowledge and experience to undertake their works for yourselves	
11.2 Will you be engaging or commission other persons to carry out designs on your behalf for this project [If so, please provide details of them and how you monitor their activities]:	
12 Accident Reporting, Enforcement and Investigation	
12.1 Please provide details on how you record and investigate accidents.	
12.2 Please provide details of any intervention or enforcement action taken over the last 5 years and actions taken to prevent recurrence.	
Further information	
Please provide any further information which you think will assist in assessing your skills, knowledge, experience and organisational capability.	

We undertake to provide the designated designer adequate time and technical support facilities to fulfil the requirements under Regulations 8, 9 and 10 of the Construction (Design and Management) Regulations 2015.

Signed:

On behalf of (Company Name):

Date:

Signed:
.....

Date:
.....

Director/Partner Responsible for Health & Safety

Exhibit 3: A sample of standard questionnaire for Principal Contractor’s organisational capability assessment

Questionnaire Checklist	Response/Comment
1 Health and Safety Policy	
1.1 Provide a copy of your Health and Safety Policy Statement.	
1.2 Provide a copy of your management organisation chart, complete with details of the health and safety team.	
2 Arrangements	
2.1 Provide details of your company Management System, in particular your Health and Safety Management System and any other arrangements for putting the Health and Safety Policy into effect.	
3 Competent Advice	
3.1 Please provide the name and competency details of your source of health and safety advice.	
4 Training and Information	
4.1 Provide details of a Health and Safety training culture to include records, certificates and adequate H&S induction training for site based personnel.	
4.2 Provide details of an active CPD programme.	
5 Individual Qualifications and Experience	
5.1 Provide details (names and CV’s) of key project personnel identifying their skills, knowledge, experience and training to carry out and manage the works.	
5.2 Provide evidence of experience with similar projects for project personnel.	
5.3 Give brief details of similar projects undertaken (locations, description, dates, size and cost) by the company. Include a reference contact for previous Clients.	
6 Monitoring, audit and review	

6.1 Provide details of the monitoring, audit and review procedures for your health and safety systems. Include evidence of any audits and the management responses.	
7 Resources and workforce involvement	
7.1 Give details on the number of competent personnel available to work on the project.	
7.2 Provide details of the technical resources available to assist project personnel in the implementation of the project. (e.g. computing, health and safety guidance, specialist technical links with external experts etc.)	
7.3 Provide evidence of health and safety consultation with workforce (names of safety representatives, records of health and safety meetings/committees etc).	
8 Accident reporting, enforcement & investigation	
8.1 Give details on the way in which you record and investigate accidents and incidents, giving details of the last 2 accidents and actions taken to prevent recurrence.	
8.2 Provide details of any enforcement action taken over the last 5 years and actions taken to put matters right.	
8.3 Provide details of your accident statistics for the last 3 years and their basis.	
9 Sub-contracting, consulting procedures	
9.1 Provide evidence showing how you ensure sub-contractors/consultants are competent.	
9.2 Give details showing how you monitor the performance of subcontractors.	
10 Risk assessment	
10.1 Provide evidence showing how the company will identify significant H&S risks and how they will be controlled.	
10.2 Provide samples of risk assessments/safe systems of work/method statements.	

11 Co-operation and co-ordination	
11.1 Provide evidence of how the company co-ordinates its work with others.	
12 Further information	
12.1 Provide any further information which you think will help assess your competence and resources	

Exhibit 4: Simple project responsibility matrix

Project participant	Organisation	Role
Client	Mr John Smith	Project funding
Project Manager	Emerald Ltd	Project administration and management
Project Architect	Predios Architects	Architectural designs services
Principal Designer	Predios Architects	Design H&S risk management
Structural Engineer	Akon Ltd	Structural design services
Services Engineer	John Brown Ltd	Building services design
Cost Consultant	CSI Consult	Project cost management
Principal Contractor	Consar Ltd	Construction H&S risk management
Main Contractor	Consar Ltd	Construction services

Exhibit 5a: Excerpts of the Designer CDM Options Matrix indicating the site plan, vehicular access and materials storage arrangements

Designer CDM Options Matrix - Hazard Identification and Significant Risk Management						ALL SIGNIFICANT RISKS				
Project & No:-	20 ROW COURT		11500	Work Stage :- 4		Revision & Date:	2 nd Issue	Nov.3 rd 2017		
HAZARDS and SIGNIFICANT RISKS	BUILDING FORM, MATERIAL, , ACTIVITY, LOCATION		ELIMINATE or AVOID risks (During early design stages) SFARP		REDUCE or MINIMIZE risks ALARP by :- (During all design stages) Safe systems of work & protection >		INFORMATION To be provided with the design eg Specialist Design & client input	CONTROL METHODS Contractor or Client Manage - ment Systems	ACTIONS & DATES and OTHER SPECIALIST GUIDANCE & COMMENTS Eg. References	
1.2 ROW COURT VEHICULAR ACCESS , EXISTING GARAGES AND PARKED CARS, RIGHTS OF WAY , STORAGE OF MATERIALS, SITE WELFARE FACILITIES			Principal Contractor and client to agree a site set-up methodology for all stages of the project. Subcontractors to be advised of the "restricted" site constraints. Vaults below the Row housing or the Horseley River Tunnel might impact upon the design. Team may need to investigate further.. Existing WC and handbasin retained at 1st floor level until new WC provided at Ground level.	Site Set-up plan to be drawn for Construction Phase Plan for demolition, propping , basement construction, upper floor works and roofing stages, plus interior fit out stage.	Project Team to discuss implications of site set-up on design , cost or safety. Conveyor of excavated material to be used to discharge into skip in Row Court. Loading of full skips and removal lorries on the Horseley Tunnel to be considered to avoid potential collapse. (See attached photograph)		Storage container to be provided by contractor on pavement/road to contain materials, tools, equipment and operatives possessions.			
Team Sign -off status	Client	Emerald Ltd	Architect	Predios Architects	Struct. Eng	Akon Ltd	Services Eng	John Brown	P. Contractor	Consar Ltd
Others	Dev..		PD	Predios Architects	Landscape		Cost Consultant	CSI Consult		

Exhibit 5b: Excerpts of the Designer CDM Options Matrix indicating the subterranean river tunnel underneath Row Court access road

Designer CDM Options Matrix - Hazard Identification and Significant Risk Management				ALL SIGNIFICANT RISKS			
Project & No:-	20 ROW COURT	11500	Work Stage :-	4	Revision & Date:	2 nd Issue	Nov.3 rd 2017
HAZARDS and SIGNIFICANT RISKS	BUILDING FORM, MATERIAL, , ACTIVITY, LOCATION	ELIMINATE or AVOID risks (During early design stages) SFARP	REDUCE or MINIMIZE risks ALARP by :- (During all design stages) Safe systems of work & protection >		INFORMATION To be provided with the design eg Specialist Design & client input	CONTROL METHODS Contractor or Client Manage - ment Systems	ACTIONS & DATES and OTHER SPECIALIST GUIDANCE & COMMENTS Eg. References
4.3.1 PUBLIC RIVER/SEWER LOCATION IN ROW COURT					Beulah Water letter dated 2 nd February 2017- Manhole cover levels and invert levels included. Historically this included the Horsely River. Dimensions and load bearing capacity of brick tunnel to be researched to ensure no impact is likely on basement or façade retention construction and skip loadings.		Client has been advised that "there is no apparent risk from this sewer on the property or basement construction works." Copy letter of confirmation from authorities requested for reference in this document.

Team Sign -off status	Client	Emerald Ltd	Architect	Predios Architects	Struct. Eng	Akon Ltd	Services Eng	John Brown	P. Contractor	Consar Ltd
Others	Dev..		PD	Predios Architects	Landscape		Cost Consultant	CSI Consult		

Exhibit 5c: Excerpts of the Designer CDM Options Matrix indicating access restrictions due to narrow arches and for demolition works

Designer CDM Options Matrix - Hazard Identification and Significant Risk Management							ALL SIGNIFICANT RISKS				
Project & No:-		20 ROW COURT		11500	Work Stage :- 4		Revision & Date:	2 nd Issue	Nov.3 rd 2017		
HAZARDS and SIGNIFICANT RISKS	BUILDING FORM, MATERIAL, , ACTIVITY, LOCATION	ELIMINATE or AVOID risks (During early design stages) SFARP	REDUCE or MINIMIZE risks ALARP by :- (During all design stages) Safe systems of work & protection >			INFORMATION To be provided with the design eg Specialist Design & client input	CONTROL METHODS Contractor or Client Manage- ment Systems	ACTIONS & DATES and OTHER SPECIALIST GUIDANCE & COMMENTS Eg. References			
1.2.1 ROW COURT ACCESS						Width, height and gradient of Mews access routes to be established on site to agree size of vehicles and plant accessing the Row Court. Large "Muckaway" or Skip lorries may not be able to gain access. Method of removal of soil to be clarified in Construction phase plan.					
1.3 ROOF REMOVAL AND OTHER DEMOLITION WORKS AND CONSTRUCTION WORKS, WITHIN A VERY TIGHT SITE ACCESS AREA.	Access to front and rear mansard/parapet gutters to be considered. Front, from ladder access from Row court, but rear gutter is very inaccessible without use of telescopic/hinged MEWP. Roof mounted eyebolts and work restraint system possible but needs trained workers and annual maintenance checks</p>		<p>Additional site survey information required of courtyards, surrounding mews and buildings. Protective suspended scaffolding, netting or fans to be provided to rear elevation to prevent materials or persons falling into lightwells.</p> <p>Simplification of roof structure to pitch to front only would be beneficial but may incur planning issues with consequent delays or raising the party wall issues. Omitted for Planning reasons</p>								
Team Sign-off status	Client	Emerald Ltd	Architect	Predios Architects	Struct. Eng	Akon Ltd	Services Eng	John Brown	P. Contractor	Consar Ltd	
Others	Dev..		PD	Predios Architects	Landscape		Cost Consultant	CSI Consult			

Exhibit 5d: Excerpts of the Designer CDM Options Matrix indicating existing survey drawings of ground floor, first floor and roof plans

Designer CDM Options Matrix - Hazard Identification and Significant Risk Management							ALL SIGNIFICANT RISKS				
Project & No:-	20 ROW COURT		11500	Work Stage :-	4	Revision & Date:	2 nd Issue	Nov. 3 rd 2017			
HAZARDS and SIGNIFICANT RISKS	BUILDING FORM, MATERIAL, , ACTIVITY, LOCATION	ELIMINATE or AVOID risks (During early design stages) SFARP	REDUCE or MINIMIZE risks ALARP by :- (During all design stages) Safe systems of work & protection >			INFORMATION To be provided with the design eg Specialist Design & client input	CONTROL METHODS Contractor or Client Manage - ment Systems	ACTIONS & DATES and OTHER SPECIALIST GUIDANCE & COMMENTS Eg. References			
1.4 EXISTING SURVEY DRAWINGS TO BE ANALYSED FOR STRUCTURAL STABILITY DURING DEMOLITION AND RE-CONSTRUCTION	<p>Demolition/refurbishment asbestos survey to be completed by client or principal contractor prior to hard strip or demolition works</p> </div>										
	<p style="text-align: right;">First Floor</p>										
	<p style="text-align: right;">Ground Floor</p>										
Team Sign -off status	Client	Emeral Ltd	Architect	Predios Architects	Struct. Eng	Akon Ltd	Services Eng	John Brown	P. Contractor	Consar Ltd	
Others	Dev..		PD	Predios Architects	Landscape		Cost Consultant	CSI Consult			

Exhibit 5e: Excerpts of the Designer CDM Options Matrix indicating the proposed basement drawings

Designer CDM Options Matrix - Hazard Identification and Significant Risk Management							ALL SIGNIFICANT RISKS																									
Project & No:-	20 ROW COURT		11500	Work Stage :- 4			Revision & Date:	2 nd Issue	Nov. 3 rd 2017																							
HAZARDS and SIGNIFICANT RISKS	BUILDING FORM, MATERIAL, , ACTIVITY, LOCATION	ELIMINATE or AVOID risks (During early design stages) SFARP	REDUCE or MINIMIZE risks ALARP by :- (During all design stages) Safe systems of work & protection >			INFORMATION To be provided with the design eg Specialist Design & client input	CONTROL METHODS Contractor or Client Manage - ment Systems	ACTIONS & DATES and OTHER SPECIALIST GUIDANCE & COMMENTS Eg. References																								
2.0 SCHEME DRAWINGS 2.1 BASEMENT	<p>1 PROPOSED BASEMENT FLOOR GA PLAN (MF1)</p> <p>2 PROPOSED BASEMENT FLOOR GA PLAN (MF2)</p>						<p> Proximity to Main Sewer /Westbourne River to be checked prior to excavations. To avoid possibility of flooding or collapse</p> <p> Existing Electrical and Gas services to be located and isolated. Safe location and configuration of distribution board required.</p> <p> Safe excavation methods to be adopted especially in the temporary completion stage</p>																									
	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>Team Sign -off status</td> <td>Client</td> <td>Emerald Ltd</td> <td>Architect</td> <td>Predios Architects</td> <td>Struct. Eng</td> <td>Akon Ltd</td> <td>Services Eng</td> <td>John Brown</td> <td>P. Contractor</td> <td>Consar Ltd</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Others</td> <td>Dev..</td> <td></td> <td>PD</td> <td>Predios Architects</td> <td>Landscape</td> <td></td> <td>Cost Consultant</td> <td>CSI Consult</td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> </table>											Team Sign -off status	Client	Emerald Ltd	Architect	Predios Architects	Struct. Eng	Akon Ltd	Services Eng	John Brown	P. Contractor	Consar Ltd	Others	Dev..		PD	Predios Architects	Landscape		Cost Consultant	CSI Consult	
Team Sign -off status	Client	Emerald Ltd	Architect	Predios Architects	Struct. Eng	Akon Ltd	Services Eng	John Brown	P. Contractor	Consar Ltd																						
Others	Dev..		PD	Predios Architects	Landscape		Cost Consultant	CSI Consult																								

Exhibit 5f: Excerpts of the Designer CDM Options Matrix indicating the proposed ground floor drawings

Designer CDM Options Matrix - Hazard Identification and Significant Risk Management							ALL SIGNIFICANT RISKS				
Project & No:-	20 ROW COURT		11500	Work Stage :-	4		Revision & Date:	2 nd Issue	Nov. 3 rd 2017		
HAZARDS and SIGNIFICANT RISKS	BUILDING FORM, MATERIAL, , ACTIVITY, LOCATION	ELIMINATE or AVOID risks (During early design stages) SFARP	REDUCE or MINIMIZE risks ALARP by :- (During all design stages) Safe systems of work & protection >		INFORMATION To be provided with the design eg Specialist Design & client input	CONTROL METHODS Contractor or Client Manage - ment Systems	ACTIONS & DATES and OTHER SPECIALIST GUIDANCE & COMMENTS Eg. References				
2.2 GROUND FLOOR PLANS	<p>Large Items of Furniture or Fittings-Type , size and weight for manual lifting of furniture to be considered in relation to size and opening of winder staircases eg. Double beds, sofas and oval bath (prior to installation).</p>										
	<p>Skylight in floor to be adequately protected and safety signed during construction to prevent falls through to basement</p>										
Team Sign-off status	Client	Emerald Ltd	Architect	Predios Architects	Struct. Eng	Akon Ltd	Services Eng	John Brown	P. Contractor	Consar Ltd	
Others	Dev..		PD	Predios Architects	Landscape		Cost Consultant	CSI Consult			

Exhibit 5g: Excerpts of the Designer CDM Options Matrix indicating the structural details of the basement

Designer CDM Options Matrix - Hazard Identification and Significant Risk Management							ALL SIGNIFICANT RISKS			
Project & No:-	20 ROW COURT		11500	Work Stage :- 4		Revision & Date:	2 nd Issue	Nov. 3 rd 2017		
HAZARDS and SIGNIFICANT RISKS	BUILDING FORM, MATERIAL, , ACTIVITY, LOCATION	ELIMINATE or AVOID risks (During early design stages) SFARP	REDUCE or MINIMIZE risks ALARP by :- (During all design stages) Safe systems of work & protection >		INFORMATION To be provided with the design eg Specialist Design & client input	CONTROL METHODS Contractor or Client Manage - ment Systems	ACTIONS & DATES and OTHER SPECIALIST GUIDANCE & COMMENTS Eg. References			
3.0 STRUCTURAL DETAILS 3.1 BASEMENT	<p>The image contains two main structural drawings. The top drawing is a plan view of the basement layout for units 1 & 2, showing walls, slabs, and reinforcement details. The bottom drawing is a section view of the ground floor layout for units 1 & 2, showing the relationship between the basement and the ground floor, including load-bearing walls and structural supports. Both drawings include numerous callouts and notes detailing construction requirements and material specifications.</p>						<p>Structural support and excavation method statement and propping details to be agreed with structural engineer or temporary works coordinator and Principal Contractor prior to commencement on site.</p>			
Team Sign-off status	Client	Emerald Ltd	Architect	Predios Architects	Struct. Eng	Akon Ltd	Services Eng	John Brown	P. Contractor	Consar Ltd
Others	Dev..		PD	Predios Architects	Landscape		Cost Consultant	CSI Consult		

Exhibit 5h: Excerpts of the Designer CDM Options Matrix indicating some minor strip out details

Designer CDM Options Matrix - Hazard Identification and Significant Risk Management							ALL SIGNIFICANT RISKS			
Project & No:-		20 ROW COURT		11500	Work Stage :- 4		Revision & Date:		2 nd Issue	Nov. 3 rd 2017
HAZARDS and SIGNIFICANT RISKS	BUILDING FORM, MATERIAL, , ACTIVITY, LOCATION		ELIMINATE or AVOID risks (During early design stages) SFARP	REDUCE or MINIMIZE risks ALARP by :- (During all design stages) Safe systems of work & protection >			INFORMATION To be provided with the design eg Specialist Design & client input	CONTROL METHODS Contractor or Client Manage - ment Systems	ACTIONS & DATES and OTHER SPECIALIST GUIDANCE & COMMENTS Eg. References	
4.1 STRIP OUT/ DEMOLITION DETAILS	<p>Internal condition</p> <p>Floor boards being removed</p> <p>Lath and plaster ceilings being removed</p> <p>All electrics isolated</p> <p>Sanitary appliances being removed</p> <p>All lead painted skirtings, doors, architraves, picture rails to be removed. Existing windows retained</p>			Floor boards and partitioning stripped out	Retained WC at 1 st floor level				Method of providing Site Welfare facilities eg. WC to be considered if all interior to be removed together.	
4.2 CDM OBJECTIVES	<p>Small to medium enterprise contractor will be carrying out the works .</p> <p>Relatively commonplace construction techniques included in the design.</p> <p>Competent contractor to be appointed by team to ensure safety procedures are carried out</p> <p>Basement construction and façade retention details to be agreed in detail with Principal Contractor prior to commencement on site</p>									
4.3 SITE PLAN	ROADS UNLOADING AREAS WATER MAINS DRAINAGE RUNS POWER CABLES UTILITY RUNS EXCAVATIONS VAULTS, TUNNEL		Site hazards cannot be eliminated	Detailed site survey required to identify all site hazards and associated risks to the construction project and future user			Fully annotated site plan required that relates proposed building and site-works to the site conditions	Contractor to liaise with client and design team on key issues	CLIENT to provide detailed site survey with existing features, and any known below ground hazards. PRIOR TO DETAILED COSTINGS AND START ON SITE	
Team Sign -off status	Client	Emerald Ltd	Architect	Predios Architects	Struct. Eng	Akon Ltd	Services Eng	John Brown	P. Contractor	Consar Ltd
Others	Dev..		PD	Predios Architects	Landscape		Cost Consultant	CSI Consult		

Exhibit 5i: Excerpts of the Designer CDM Options Matrix indicating some planning conditions and restrictions

Designer CDM Options Matrix - Hazard Identification and Significant Risk Management							ALL SIGNIFICANT RISKS									
Project & No:-		20 ROW COURT		11500		Work Stage :- 4		Revision & Date:		2 nd Issue		Nov. 3 rd 2017				
HAZARDS and SIGNIFICANT RISKS		BUILDING FORM, MATERIAL, , ACTIVITY, LOCATION		ELIMINATE or AVOID risks (During early design stages) SFARP		REDUCE or MINIMIZE risks ALARP by :- (During all design stages) Safe systems of work & protection >		INFORMATION To be provided with the design eg Specialist Design & client input		CONTROL METHODS Contractor or Client Manage - ment Systems		ACTIONS & DATES and OTHER SPECIALIST GUIDANCE & COMMENTS Eg. References				
7.1 PLANNING CONDITIONS- CONSTRUCTION TIMES		2		<p>Except for basement excavation work, you must carry out any building work which can be heard at the boundary of the site only:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * between 08.00 and 18.00 Monday to Friday; * between 08.00 and 13.00 on Saturday; and * not at all on Sundays, bank holidays and public holidays. <p>You must carry out basement excavation work only:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * between 08.00 and 18.00 Monday to Friday; and * not at all on Saturdays, Sundays, bank holidays and public holidays. <p>Noisy work must not take place outside these hours unless we have agreed that there are very special circumstances (for example, to meet police traffic restrictions, in an emergency or in the interests of public safety). (C11BA)</p> <p><u>Reason:</u> To protect the environment of neighbouring residents. This is as set out in CS28 and CS31 of our Core Strategy that we adopted in January 2011 and ENV 6 of our Unitary Development Plan that we adopted in January 2007. (R11AC)</p>						Construction times to be strictly adhered to by contractor.						
7.2 PLANNING CONDITION CONSTRUCTION METHOD STATEMENT		11		<p>No development shall take place, including any works of demolition, until a Construction Method Statement has been submitted to, and approved in writing by, the local planning authority. The approved Statement shall be adhered to throughout the construction period. The Statement shall provide for:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> i. the parking of vehicles of site operatives and visitors ii. loading and unloading of plant and materials iii. storage of plant and materials used in constructing the development iv. the erection and maintenance of security hoarding including decorative displays and facilities for public viewing, where appropriate v. wheel washing facilities vi. measures to control the emission of dust and dirt during construction vii. a scheme for recycling/disposing of waste resulting from demolition and construction works viii. a condition survey of the cobbled mews outside the application site before and after works take place and include measures for repairing any damage caused . <p><u>Reason:</u> To safeguard the amenities of adjoining residents during the excavation and construction of the basement extension as set out in CS28 and CS31 of our Core Strategy that we adopted in January 2011 and policies ENV6 and ENV13 of our adopted Unitary Development Plan that we adopted in January 1997.</p>		Scaffolding details to be agreed with Beulah Council		Method Statements required from Contractor prior to start on site.								
Team Sign -off status		Client	Emerald Ltd		Architect	Predios Ltd		Struct. Eng	Akon Ltd		Services Eng	John Brown		P. Contractor	Consar Ltd	
Others		Dev..			PD	Predios Ltd		Landscape			Cost Consultant	CSI Consult				

Exhibit 6: A sample of checklist for Construction Phase Plan (CPP) review

	Yes	No	Comment
1 Description of the Project			
1.1 Project Description & Programme			
1.2 Client, Designers, Principal Designer, Principal Contractor, Other Consultants/Contractors/Organisations			
1.3 Existing Records and Plans			
1.4 Register of Reviews			
2 Management of the Work			
2.1 Management Structure and Responsibilities			
2.2 Health and Safety Goals			
2.3 Arrangements for Monitoring and Review of H&S performance			
2.4 Arrangements for regular liaison amongst parties on site			
2.5 Consultation with the workforce			
2.6 Exchange of design information between the Client, Designers, Principal Designer and Contractors			
2.7 Handling design changes during the project			
2.8 The selection and control of contractors			
2.9 The exchange of health and safety information between contractors			
2.10 Site Security			
2.11 Site induction			
2.12 On-site training			
2.13 Competence of workforce			
2.14 Welfare facilities			
2.15 First aid			
2.16 The reporting and investigation of accidents and incidents including near misses			
2.17 The production and approval of risk assessments and method statements			
2.18 Site rules (including drug and alcohol policy)			
2.19 Fire and emergency procedures			
3 Arrangements for Controlling Significant Site Safety Risks			

3.1 Delivery and removal of materials and work equipment			
3.2 Dealing with services - water, electricity and gas, including temporary electrical installations and overhead cables			
3.3 Accommodating adjacent land use			
3.4 Stability of structures during work, including temporary structures.			
3.5 Dealing with existing unstable structures			
3.6 Preventing falls			
3.7 Work with or near fragile materials			
3.8 Control of lifting operations			
3.9 The maintenance of plant and equipment			
3.10 Work on Excavations			
3.11 Poor ground conditions			
3.12 Wells, underground earthworks and tunnels			
3.13 Work on or near water			
3.14 Work involving diving			
3.15 Work in Caissons or confined spaces.			
3.16 Compressed air working			
3.17 Work involving explosives			
3.18 Traffic routes and segregation of vehicles and pedestrians			
3.19 Storage of materials and work equipment			
3.20 Storage of hazardous materials			
3.21 Other site safety risks/procedures identified.			
3.22 Site Specific Risk Register			
4 Arrangements for Controlling Significant Site Health Risks			
4.1 Removal of asbestos			
4.2 Dealing with contaminated land			
4.3 Manual handling			
4.4 Use of hazardous substances			
4.5 Reducing noise and vibration			
4.6 Work with ionising radiation			

4.7 Exposure to UV radiation from the sun			
4.8 Other significant health risks			
5 Health & Safety File			
5.1 Layout and format;			
5.2 Arrangements for the collection and gathering of information			
5.3 Storage of information.			

Exhibit 7: Restricted roof gutter and openable roof light in the mansard roof

HAZARDS and SIGNIFICANT RISKS	BUILDING FORM, MATERIAL, , ACTIVITY, LOCATION	ELIMINATE or AVOID risks (During early design stages) SFARP	REDUCE or MINIMIZE risks ALARP by :- (During all design stages) Safe systems of work & protection >	INFORMATION To be provided with the design eg Specialist Design & client input	CONTROL METHODS Contractor or Client Manage - ment Systems	ACTIONS & DATES and OTHER SPECIALIST GUIDANCE & COMMENTS Eg. References
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2.5- SECTIONS UNITS 1 & 2

Roof-lights above bedroom and stair ideally to be non-fragile to prevent the possibility of people on the roof falling through during inspection or maintenance. Cleaning from roof only with harness and attachment

Work restraint harness and lanyard attachment points on roof to prevent falls during maintenance of rear gutter

Alternatively rear wall extended to 150mm above top roof level and rear gutter removed. Planning issues to be considered, but minimal change should not need reapplication. After consultation with planners this option was discounted due to likely planning objections from neighbours and officers.

Exhibit 8: Standard architectural agenda for meetings

Design Team Meeting Agenda (CDM specific items):-

1. CDM issues to be taken with all report/agenda items eg. Client, architect, structures, services, landscape, fire, etc. Not as a stand-alone subject.
2. All CDM Significant issues (risks and benefits) to be identified and captured in Schedule and CDM analysis report & drawings, with lead action owner and priority (RAG) indicated.
3. CDM Options Matrix items to be part of focus for meeting discussions
4. All CDM Significant issues to be prioritised and discussed by whole team in visual project context and resolution/mitigation/future action agreed and recorded.
5. Pre-Construction Information/ CDM Options Matrix to be updated and issued, as project issues dictate, throughout the project, and at end of Work Stages.
6. Health and Safety File format and progress to be agreed from the start of the project.

Exhibit 9a: Proposed original single pitch roof design and modified option due to planning restrictions

HAZARDS and SIGNIFICANT RISKS	BUILDING FORM, MATERIAL, , ACTIVITY, LOCATION	ELIMINATE or AVOID risks (During early design stages) SFARP	REDUCE or MINIMIZE risks ALARP by :- (During all design stages) Safe systems of work & protection >	INFORMATION To be provided with the design eg Specialist Design & client input	CONTROL METHODS Contractor or Client Manage - ment Systems	ACTIONS & DATES and OTHER SPECIALIST GUIDANCE & COMMENTS Eg. References
	<p>single pitch lead roof (1:80 fall)</p> <p>kerbed up stand</p> <p>lead wrapped verge board</p> <p>extended wall</p> <p>proposed top of coping</p> <p>proposed gutter</p> <p>proposed mansard profile</p> <p>existing wall</p> <p>530</p> <p>Black denotes current proposal</p> <p>Blue denotes amended roof profile</p> <p>2 ENLARGED SECTION</p>					<p>Possible alternative detail not agreed with Planners for reasons of Rights of Light</p>

Exhibit 9b: Specific locations of potential sunlight blockage to adjoining property due to height increment of roof gutter upstand

Locations of potential blockage of sunlight into an adjoining property due to increment in height of roof gutter upstand